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Effect Of Portfolio Management Models On Return Optimization In Real Estate Investments In South-East Nigeria

¹Hillary Amaechi Ajogwu & ²Esv. (Professor) Charles C. Egolum (FNIVS).

Department of Estate Management,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria
¹E-mail: ajogwuhillaryamaechi@gmail.com / Phone: 09123340350
²E-mail: cc.egolum@unizik.edu.ng / Phone: 07060956767

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of portfolio management models on return optimization and real estate investment performance in South-East Nigeria. Despite a growing volume of real estate investments in the region, many investors continue to experience suboptimal returns due to inadequate adoption of structured portfolio strategies. Portfolio management models such as Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT), Value-at-Risk (VaR), and scenario planning have proven effective globally in mitigating risks and optimizing returns, yet their implementation in emerging Nigerian markets remains limited. Using a descriptive survey design, the study employed a total enumeration sampling technique targeting 544 registered Estate Surveyors and Valuers across Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo states. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression techniques. The results reveal a statistically significant but modest positive relationship between the use of portfolio management models and return optimization ($R^2 = 0.011$, $p = 0.017$), as well as investment performance ($R^2 = 0.025$, $p = 0.007$). These findings suggest that even limited application of formal portfolio tools can enhance real estate investment outcomes. Based on the findings it was recommended that there should be increased adoption of quantitative models, professional training, and regulatory support to strengthen investment performance in the region. The findings contribute to localized knowledge on portfolio strategies and offer practical implications for policymakers, investors, and real estate professionals in emerging markets.

Keywords: Portfolio management models, real estate investment, return optimization, South-East Nigeria, Modern Portfolio Theory, investment performance, diversification, risk management.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Portfolio management models is important in optimizing returns and mitigating risks in real estate investments, especially within dynamic and volatile markets. These models, which include techniques such as asset diversification, value-at-risk (VaR), beta optimization, and scenario planning, offer investors a systematic approach to balance expected returns against associated risks. In global and emerging markets alike, their strategic application has been shown to significantly improve investment outcomes and capital preservation. Oloke et al., (2022) indicated that many investors in this region continue to rely on traditional, informal methods of investment decision-making without incorporating quantitative tools

that enhance return optimization (Oloke et al., 2022; Nnamani, 2017). As a result, they often face performance volatility, capital erosion, and missed opportunities for return maximization. Despite the growing importance of the real estate sector in the South-East, there is limited empirical research evaluating how portfolio management models are applied and the extent to which they influence actual investment performance. Moreover, most available studies either focus on broader financial markets or are limited to Lagos and South-Western Nigeria, making them less applicable to the socio-economic and investment realities of the South-East. Integrated portfolio modeling, when tailored to local market dynamics, has the potential to improve resource allocation, minimize unsystematic risks, and stabilize investor returns across various property asset classes. Therefore, understanding the effectiveness of portfolio management models in optimizing real estate returns is essential for developing robust investment strategies and guiding investor behavior in the South-East real estate market.

Despite the rising volume of real estate investments in South-East Nigeria, many investors continue to experience suboptimal returns, largely due to poor adoption of formal portfolio management models. The region's real estate sector faces distinct challenges such as fluctuating market demand, limited access to capital, regulatory delays, and asset concentration risks all of which demand structured portfolio optimization strategies. However, investors and firms often lack the technical expertise or tools necessary to implement quantitative models such as scenario simulations, beta analysis, or diversification algorithms, which are central to return optimization.

While some studies have examined real estate investment performance in other regions of Nigeria (Odeyomi et al., 2023; Akinola, 2023), there remains a critical research gap regarding how portfolio management practices affect investment returns in the South-East. Specifically, empirical evidence is lacking on whether and how portfolio models improve return outcomes in this regional context. Without this understanding, investors are left to make decisions based on intuition or outdated methods, increasing exposure to risk and reducing long-term profitability.

To bridge this gap, this study seeks to investigate the effect of portfolio management models on return optimization in real estate investments within South-East Nigeria. It also aims to examine the relationship between the adoption of these models and overall investment performance, in the quest to fill this gaps, the study aims to;

1. assess the effect of portfolio management models on optimization of returns.
2. examine the relationship between the use of portfolio models and real estate investment performance.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviewed the related literature of the study, it commenced by reviewing the variables of the study, it further reviewed relevant theories and finally reviewed related empirical studies.

2.1.1 Portfolio Management Models

Portfolio management models in real estate are strategic tools designed to allocate investment capital across a range of property assets in order to optimize returns and minimize risk exposure. Modern portfolio theory (MPT), when applied to real estate, allows investors to consider systemic and unsystemic risks across asset classes such as residential, commercial, and industrial properties. Despite its relevance, the practical adoption of such models remains limited, particularly in emerging markets like Nigeria. Recent studies highlight that institutional investors increasingly rely on simulation-based risk models and Markowitz-style portfolio optimization to assess risk-return structures of property holdings (Armonat & Pfnuer, 2016). These models replace reliance on historical market data with project-based simulation techniques, offering improved flexibility in volatile real estate environments. In corporate real estate management, a portfolio approach enables decision-makers to manage assets at a macro level, ensuring strategic alignment and maximizing functional and financial value (Varcoe, 2020). Despite global advances, Nigerian real estate firms often do not incorporate these sophisticated tools. Instead, investment

decisions are still largely intuitive, constrained by data gaps, limited technical expertise, and absence of robust market analytics (Oloke et al., 2022). This results in poor diversification and inability to hedge against market downturns.

2.1.2 Optimization of Returns

Return optimization in real estate refers to strategies aimed at maximizing profit while managing risk across varying market cycles. Techniques include quantitative asset allocation, diversification across property types and locations, and dynamic rebalancing in response to market signals. Optimization tools such as the Sharpe ratio, beta coefficient, and value-at-risk (VaR) are commonly used to quantify and adjust risk exposures. Agava et al. (2023) confirmed that diversified residential real estate portfolios were significantly more resilient during inflationary shocks, demonstrating how strategic allocation can shield investments from systemic risks. The study revealed that portfolios that lacked diversity especially those concentrated in single asset types recorded reduced performance in adverse economic periods. Meanwhile, scenario modeling as a planning tool allows investors to simulate different economic or regulatory outcomes and adjust portfolios accordingly (Awa et al., 2020). However, in Nigeria, the adoption of these tools remains limited. Many firms lack the financial analytics capabilities required to operationalize optimization frameworks effectively. According to recent findings, even when models are known, their use is often informal or partial, limiting their impact on actual return enhancement (Oloke et al., 2022).

2.1.3 Real Estate Investment Performance

Real estate investment performance is typically assessed through metrics such as rental yield, capital appreciation, internal rate of return (IRR), and net present value (NPV). Performance is influenced by a combination of macroeconomic conditions (e.g., inflation, exchange rates), market dynamics (e.g., demand-supply imbalances), and project-specific factors (e.g., construction delays, title disputes). Empirical studies have shown that inadequate risk management practices and poor application of portfolio models contribute to inconsistent returns in the Nigerian real estate sector. For instance, Oloke and Adenekan (2025) found that macro-financial risks like inflation and currency volatility were major impediments to predictable investment performance in Lagos-based projects. These risks were rarely modeled or quantified in early-stage investment appraisals, resulting in delayed project delivery and financial underperformance.

In addition, Agava et al. (2023) emphasized that asset-class diversification improves portfolio stability, especially during periods of market stress. However, the study was limited to residential real estate, with gaps in commercial and mixed-use investments, and did not explore geographic nuances such as those specific to South-East Nigeria. This underscores the need for regionally tailored research to fully understand performance dynamics in underrepresented markets like Enugu or Awka.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Integrated Risk Management (IRM) Theory, which advocates for a holistic approach to identifying, analyzing, and mitigating risks across all organizational levels. IRM integrates operational, financial, and strategic risk factors into a unified decision-making framework, offering a more comprehensive understanding of investment exposures. Lam (2003) defines IRM as a proactive strategy that enhances business resilience by combining traditional siloed risk functions into an interconnected risk architecture. The relevance of IRM to real estate lies in its ability to synthesize project-level uncertainties such as cost overruns and approval delays with broader portfolio strategies such as diversification and asset rebalancing. This allows for more robust planning, execution, and performance evaluation. In contrast, Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT), while widely applied in finance, focuses primarily on statistical diversification to minimize risk and maximize return. However, MPT tends to overlook operational and developmental risks specific to real estate, such as title conflicts or regulatory delays [(Aro-Gordon & Dauda, 2014)]. As such, IRM offers a more suitable lens for analyzing

Nigerian real estate investments, where both financial and operational risks significantly influence outcomes.

Further supporting this approach, Jagun (2020) advocated for embedding real-time risk feedback mechanisms in real estate feasibility studies, aligning with IRM's emphasis on adaptability and continuous monitoring. The integration of IRM into real estate investment allows for a comprehensive strategy that links micro-level risk analysis (e.g., Monte Carlo simulations, Delphi method) with macro-level investment planning (e.g., scenario-based portfolio modeling), enhancing return predictability and investor confidence.

2.3 Empirical Review

Oloke and Adenekan (2025) conducted a study titled "Investigating the Dynamics of Financial Risk Impact on Real Estate Projects in Nigeria" with the primary objective of examining how macroeconomic financial risks influence project delivery in the Nigerian real estate sector. Employing a quantitative methodology, the researchers distributed structured questionnaires to real estate professionals and conducted regression analysis to determine the impact of variables such as inflation, exchange rate volatility, and interest rate fluctuations. The study surveyed 120 participants based in Lagos, Nigeria a major urban center where real estate activity is robust. Their findings indicate that financial risks are significant contributors to both cost overruns and delivery delays in real estate projects. These risks, if unaddressed, reduce investor confidence and increase project failure rates. However, a key limitation of the study is its exclusive focus on Lagos. The results are not necessarily applicable to semi-urban regions such as Enugu, where market dynamics, investment capacity, and risk profiles may differ substantially. The authors recommend validating the findings in other Nigerian contexts for broader applicability.

Agava et al. (2023), in their study titled "Assessment of Residential Real Estate Investment in Nigeria," aimed to evaluate how portfolio diversification affects the performance of residential real estate investments. Using quantitative methods including Sharpe ratio analysis and portfolio performance modeling, the authors assessed 75 residential real estate portfolios across Lafia, a growing but less developed urban center. The study focused on determining the impact of economic shocks on portfolio stability and how diversification strategies contribute to risk mitigation. The results showed that portfolios with a broader mix of property types and locations performed better during inflationary and recessionary periods. The diversified portfolios demonstrated greater resilience and return consistency. However, the study presents a significant gap: it exclusively focused on residential assets and did not explore the performance of commercial or mixed-use properties. Furthermore, the regional focus on Lafia limits the applicability of the findings to other areas like Enugu, which may have different real estate dynamics, regulatory pressures, and economic structures.

Odeyomi et al. (2023) conducted a qualitative case study titled "Risks Associated with Real Estate Project Delivery in Nigeria," with the objective of identifying project-level risks that affect timely and cost-effective real estate development. The research focused on 10 selected real estate development projects across Lagos and Abuja, two of Nigeria's most prominent urban areas. Using in-depth case evaluations and stakeholder interviews, the study uncovered a range of project delivery risks, most notably regulatory delays, inconsistencies in planning approvals, and land tenure conflicts. These issues were most prominent during the pre-construction stage, resulting in delayed construction timelines, escalated project costs, and increased investor withdrawals. While the study offers rich insights into the bottlenecks faced during real estate project implementation, it does not investigate how these project-level risks influence broader investment performance or portfolio returns. This lack of integration into a financial or investment context is a critical gap, particularly for investors seeking to balance project execution risks with return optimization.

Akinola (2023), in the study "Evaluating the Impact of Risk Factors on Construction Performance in Nigeria," sought to identify the primary risks contributing to construction delays and budget overruns in

the Nigerian real estate sector. A mixed-method approach was employed, incorporating both qualitative interviews and quantitative analysis to gain a comprehensive understanding of risk dynamics. The research involved 95 respondents drawn from various construction and real estate firms across Nigeria, making it one of the broader nationwide studies. The findings revealed that cost overruns, approval delays, and contractor inefficiencies were the most frequent and impactful risks hindering project delivery. The study emphasized the urgent need for structured risk assessment tools to improve project outcomes. However, the major limitation lies in its narrow focus on construction performance. It does not extend its analysis to post-construction phases or evaluate how such operational risks influence financial performance or investor returns, particularly within real estate portfolios. This leaves a critical gap in understanding the full investment cycle.

Odeyemi and Lawal (2022) explored the topic “Comparative Study of Real Estate Project Risk Management Practices” to understand how real estate developers in Southwest Nigeria address project-related risks. Using a qualitative research design, the authors conducted semi-structured interviews with 15 real estate practitioners, capturing rich insights into localized practices and attitudes. The study revealed that most developers in the region employ informal and fragmented strategies such as intuitive decision-making, rescheduling, and ad hoc community engagement to manage risks. These practices often lack empirical validation and result in inconsistent risk outcomes, particularly in areas with unstable regulatory frameworks. While the study provides valuable context-specific insights, it suffers from several limitations. The sample size is relatively small, and the geographic focus is limited to the Southwest, making the findings less generalizable to other regions like Enugu. Additionally, the qualitative nature of the study does not allow for predictive modeling or quantitative assessment of how these risk practices influence long-term investment performance.

Muritala et al. (2022) conducted a quantitative survey study titled “Relative Occurrence of Risk Factors in Nigerian Real Estate” aimed at identifying and ranking the most frequent and severe risk factors in real estate project development. The researchers collected responses from 100 real estate professionals based in Lagos, using structured questionnaires to gather data. Their findings revealed that the pre-construction phase particularly in areas related to land acquisition, title verification, and planning approvals poses the highest risk exposure. These issues often cause project delays, cost escalations, and investor uncertainty. The study emphasizes the importance of early risk identification and suggests proactive planning measures. However, the study’s principal limitation lies in its exclusion of financial implications. While it effectively maps risk frequencies, it does not evaluate how these risks impact real estate investment performance or portfolio viability. Moreover, it focuses solely on Lagos, failing to capture risk dynamics in less developed but growing markets such as Enugu.

In their study “Engagement with Modern Portfolio Theory in Nigerian Real Estate Firms,” Oloke et al. (2022) assessed the extent to which real estate firms adopt quantitative portfolio management tools. Employing a quantitative survey methodology, they gathered data from 80 firms located in Lagos, a hub for real estate investment in Nigeria. The findings demonstrated a significant gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. While many firms were aware of tools such as Value-at-Risk (VaR), the Sharpe ratio, and scenario simulations, few actually utilized them in practice. Instead, firms often relied on traditional valuation methods and intuition-driven decisions. This limited adoption reduced their capacity to accurately forecast returns and respond to market volatility. A major gap identified in the study is its geographic limitation it does not assess the use of portfolio management tools in developing real estate markets like Enugu. This restricts the generalizability of its findings, especially for regions where data scarcity and technical capacity are even more pressing challenges.

Jagun (2020) in the study “Risk Intelligence in Property Feasibility Studies” proposed a conceptual shift in how risk is integrated into real estate feasibility assessments. Drawing from an extensive literature synthesis and theoretical modeling, the author argued that traditional feasibility studies are often static and fail to account for real-time risks such as regulatory changes, inflation, or stakeholder disruptions.

The study recommends embedding dynamic risk feedback loops into appraisal processes to enhance decision-making flexibility and responsiveness. This model aligns with integrated risk management frameworks and emphasizes proactive planning. However, the study is conceptual and lacks empirical testing. It does not include field data or practical case applications, making its recommendations theoretical rather than evidence-based. Moreover, it does not assess how such a framework would operate in specific Nigerian contexts like Enugu, where developer capacity and risk culture may be substantially different. Further empirical validation is needed to determine the feasibility and usability of the proposed model.

Awa et al. (2020), in their study “Property-Type and Economic Specialization for Portfolio Diversification,” explored how combining different real estate asset types and aligning them with regional economic strengths can improve portfolio performance. Using scenario analysis and comparative modeling, they evaluated 40 real estate portfolios across Nigeria. Their findings demonstrated that portfolios diversified by property type (residential, commercial, industrial) and economic region showed reduced volatility and improved risk-return profiles, especially during economic downturns. The study contributes significantly to the literature on portfolio resilience and supports the application of diversification principles in emerging markets. However, it primarily focuses on asset allocation and does not account for project-specific risks such as construction delays, title disputes, or regulatory issues. Additionally, it lacks geographic specificity, as no data from Enugu or similar emerging markets were included. The exclusion of project-level operational risks limits the comprehensiveness of the findings, suggesting the need for integrated models that consider both asset allocation and on-ground development risks.

In the study “Appraisal of Risk Factors in Commercial Real Estate,” Akinjare et al. (2018) examined how macroeconomic and regulatory risks impact commercial property investments in Nigeria. Utilizing documentary reviews and regression analysis, the researchers analyzed data from 50 real estate firms operating in Lagos. Their findings highlighted inflation, unstable government policies, and poor diversification as the most significant factors negatively affecting rental yields and capital appreciation. The study underscored the inadequacy of existing risk management frameworks and advocated for the use of scenario planning tools to better forecast returns. While the insights are valuable, the study is limited by its reliance on older data, which may not fully reflect the current realities of the Nigerian real estate market. Furthermore, the exclusive focus on Lagos means the conclusions may not apply to other regions like Enugu, where market maturity, investor behavior, and policy dynamics differ. The study also does not assess project-specific risks, which are crucial for new and developing real estate investments.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to empirically examine the effect of portfolio management models on return optimization in real estate investments across South-East Nigeria. The descriptive survey approach was deemed suitable as it facilitates the collection of structured and standardized data from a diverse group of professionals actively engaged in real estate investment, risk analysis, and portfolio planning. According to Creswell (2018), this design is particularly effective for studies seeking to understand prevailing practices, behaviors, and patterns in real-world settings such as the dynamic and evolving real estate markets found in Nigeria’s South-East region.

The target population comprised all 544 registered Estate Surveyors and Valuers operating within the five states of South-East Nigeria: Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo. These professionals were selected because of their dual roles in property valuation and strategic investment management, making them central to the adoption or neglect of portfolio management tools in real estate decision-making. As they serve as institutional advisors, market analysts, and investment consultants, their inputs are critical in understanding how portfolio models are being applied to optimize returns.

Given the manageable population size and the need for inclusive representation, the study employed a total enumeration (census) sampling technique. All 544 identified professionals were targeted in the data collection process. This method ensured comprehensive coverage and eliminated sampling error, providing robust insights into the application of portfolio strategies across the region.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, segmented into four sections: (1) demographic profile, (2) knowledge and application of portfolio management models, (3) techniques for return optimization, and (4) investment performance indicators. The instrument included both Likert-scale items and open-ended questions to capture quantitative metrics and qualitative perspectives on model usage and outcomes.

The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics including frequency distributions, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize respondents' characteristics and general trends in portfolio model adoption. To test the study's hypotheses, particularly H01 (no significant effect of portfolio models on return optimization) and H03 (no relationship between model use and investment performance), the study employed multiple regression analysis using SPSS software. This allowed for the assessment of predictive relationships between the use of portfolio models and real estate investment performance across the region.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section examined data presentation and analysis. The data collected was summarized and presented in the tables below. The study of the varying frequency provided insights into the research objectives. Five hundred and forty four (544) copies of the questionnaire were administered but five hundred and ten (510) were retrieved, valid and used for the analysis.

4.1 Presentation of Results

Table 4.1: Respondents Demographics

	Frequency	Percent
Male	365	71.6
Female	145	28.4
Total	510	100.0
Age		
18 - 25 years	40	7.8
26 - 35 Years	137	26.9
36 - 45 Years	293	57.5
46 Years above	40	7.8
Total	510	100.0
Educational Qualification		
SSCE	95	18.6
BSC/HND	385	75.5
Masters	30	5.8
Total	510	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	79	15.5
Married	176	34.5
Divorced	206	40.4
Widowed	33	6.5
Complicated	16	3.1
Total	510	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The respondents' demographic data shows that the majority were male, representing 71.6% (365 individuals), while females made up 28.4% (145 individuals). In terms of age, the largest group was between 36 and 45 years, comprising 57.5% (293 respondents), followed by 26-35 years at 26.9% (137 respondents). Both the 18-25 and 46 years and above age groups accounted for 7.8% each (40 respondents). Regarding educational qualifications, most respondents held a BSc/HND degree (75.5%, or 385 individuals), with 18.6% (95 respondents) having an SSCE, and 5.8% (30 respondents) holding a Master's degree. As for marital status, the highest percentage was divorced individuals at 40.4% (206 respondents), followed by married individuals at 34.5% (176 respondents). Single respondents accounted for 15.5% (79 individuals), while widowed individuals were 6.5% (33 respondents) and those with complicated marital status were 3.1% (16 respondents).

Table 4.2 Regression Analysis on the Effect of Portfolio Management Model on Optimization of Returns

H₀₁: Portfolio management models have no significant effect on the optimization of returns in real estate investments.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.106 ^a	.011	.009	4.31067

a. Predictors: (Constant), PMM

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	106.067	1	106.067	5.708	.017 ^b
	Residual	9272.368	499	18.582		
	Total	9378.435	500			

a. Dependent Variable: OR

b. Predictors: (Constant), PMM

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11.145	.823		13.545	.000
	PMM	.119	.050	.106	2.389	.017

a. Dependent Variable: OR

Model Summary

The model summary indicates that portfolio management models (PMM) account for 1.1% of the variance in return optimization (OR), as shown by the R Square value of 0.011. The Adjusted R Square of 0.009 confirms that after adjusting for the number of predictors, the explanatory power remains minimal. The standard error of the estimate is 4.31067, suggesting moderate dispersion of the observed values around the regression line.

ANOVA

The ANOVA results show that the overall regression model is statistically significant, with an F-value of 5.708 and a p-value of 0.017 ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that the predictor variable portfolio management

models (PMM) significantly explains variance in the dependent variable (optimization of returns). Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected, affirming that portfolio management models do have a statistically significant effect on return optimization.

Coefficients

The regression coefficient for portfolio management models is $\beta = 0.119$, with a t-value of 2.389 and a p-value of 0.017, indicating a positive and statistically significant relationship between the use of PMM and return optimization. This implies that for every one-unit increase in the application of portfolio management models, there is a corresponding increase in the optimization of real estate investment returns. Although the effect size is small, the direction is positive and meaningful within the context of model use.

Table 4.3 Regression Analysis on the Relationship between Use of Portfolio management models and real estate investment performance

H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between the use of portfolio management models and real estate investment performance.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.119 ^a	.025	.008	4.21073

a. Predictors: (Constant), PMM

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	102.061	1	104.067	5.708	.005 ^b
	Residual	9170.361	498	18.582		
	Total	9378.435	501			

a. Dependent Variable: RIP

b. Predictors: (Constant), PMM

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	12.130	.729		12.207	.000
	PMM	.108	.060	.103	2.273	.007

a. Dependent Variable: RIP

Model Summary

The model summary indicates a weak positive correlation between the use of portfolio management models (PMM) and real estate investment performance (RIP), with an R value of 0.119. The R Square value of 0.025 suggests that portfolio management models explain approximately 2.5% of the variation in real estate investment performance. The Adjusted R Square of 0.008 indicates that the explanatory power remains low even after adjusting for model complexity. The standard error of the estimate is 4.21073, suggesting a moderate level of prediction error.

ANOVA

The ANOVA table shows that the regression model is statistically significant, with an F-value of 5.708 and a p-value of 0.005 ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that the use of portfolio management models contributes meaningfully to explaining differences in investment performance. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) is rejected, confirming a significant relationship between PMM use and real estate investment performance.

Coefficients

The regression coefficient for PMM is $B = 0.108$, with a t-value of 2.273 and a p-value of 0.007, which is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The positive beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.103$) suggests that increased application of portfolio management models is associated with improved real estate investment performance. Though the effect size is modest, the direction is positive and significant.

4.2 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from this study provide empirical evidence that portfolio management models (PMM) have a statistically significant effect on both the optimization of returns and real estate investment performance in South-East Nigeria. While the overall explanatory power of the regression models was modest ($R^2 = 0.011$ for return optimization and $R^2 = 0.025$ for investment performance), the significance levels ($p = 0.017$ and $p = 0.007$, respectively) indicate that the use of portfolio models plays a meaningful role in improving investment outcomes, albeit to a limited extent. These results align with the findings of Agava et al. (2023), who assessed 75 residential real estate portfolios using Sharpe ratio analysis and quantitative modeling. Their study found that portfolios with broader diversification across property types and locations were more resilient during inflationary shocks and economic recessions. The present study supports this conclusion by showing that increased application of PMM contributes positively to optimizing returns suggesting that diversification and structured modeling do help shield investors from market volatility.

The findings are also consistent with Awa et al. (2020), who employed scenario analysis to demonstrate that sectoral and geographic diversification significantly enhances portfolio stability. Their study highlighted that strategic integration of property types with regional economic dynamics improves return profiles, particularly in periods of systemic shocks. Similarly, this study shows that PMMs when applied lead to improved investment outcomes, thereby reinforcing the value of structured, model-based portfolio strategies. Additionally, this study confirms the observations of Oloke et al. (2022), who surveyed 80 real estate firms in Lagos and found that many firms underutilize quantitative tools such as Value-at-Risk (VaR), Sharpe ratio, and scenario simulations. Their findings revealed a disconnect between theoretical knowledge of portfolio models and their practical application, resulting in lower capacity to mitigate risks and optimize returns. The present study extends this insight by showing that even in South-East Nigeria, where empirical studies are limited, structured use of PMMs still has a statistically significant effect thereby suggesting that broader adoption could enhance investment performance across Nigeria.

Moreover, the study aligns with the theoretical propositions of the Integrated Risk Management (IRM) framework (Lam, 2003), which advocates for a holistic approach to investment and operational risks. This theory supports the idea that micro-level project risks (such as cost overruns or regulatory delays) and macro-level portfolio strategies (such as diversification and asset rebalancing) should be integrated. The findings here lend empirical weight to IRM by demonstrating that the use of PMMs tools that inherently combine risk and return considerations correlate positively with performance outcomes.

On the contrary, this study diverges from the results of Muritala et al. (2022) and Odeyemi & Lawal (2022) to some extent. Muritala et al. focused on ranking the severity of real estate risks, particularly during pre-construction, but did not link these risks to broader investment performance. Odeyemi and Lawal, using a qualitative approach, observed a prevalence of informal and intuitive risk management methods in Southwest Nigeria, which they suggested might be ineffective but did not quantify the impact

on returns. While their work helps explain the contextual background, the current study advances the discussion by empirically establishing that where formal portfolio models are applied, there is measurable improvement in both return optimization and performance.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

This study investigated the effect of portfolio management models on return optimization and real estate investment performance in South-East Nigeria. The findings provide compelling evidence that the application of structured portfolio management models such as diversification strategies, scenario simulations, and quantitative risk-return tools has a statistically significant positive effect on both the optimization of returns and overall investment performance. Although the models accounted for a modest portion of the variance (1.1% and 2.5%, respectively), their predictive significance confirms that even minimal use of quantitative models can meaningfully influence investment outcomes. The study also affirmed the growing relevance of Integrated Risk Management (IRM) theory in the real estate context, where both operational and financial risks must be simultaneously addressed. This supports the argument that real estate investment performance is not solely driven by market trends or capital availability, but also by the structured application of portfolio optimization tools. Importantly, this research fills a notable gap in literature by offering empirical insights specific to South-East Nigeria, a region previously underrepresented in real estate investment research. The results suggest that low adoption of portfolio management models among investors and firms in the region could be contributing to the persistent problem of suboptimal returns. Therefore, scaling up the use of these models backed by data-driven strategies could significantly improve investor confidence, capital efficiency, and return sustainability in the region's real estate market.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study it is recommended that;

1. Real estate investors and firms should be encouraged to adopt well-established models such as Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT), Value-at-Risk (VaR), and scenario-based planning to enhance return optimization and mitigate portfolio risk. Regulatory agencies and professional bodies can champion this through policy incentives or compliance frameworks.
2. Stakeholders, including industry associations, real estate education providers, and regulatory institutions, should design specialized training programs that equip investors, estate surveyors, and developers with practical skills in portfolio modeling, financial forecasting, and risk-return analysis.

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